

Establishment and morphological characterization of a core collection of pathogenic fungal strains isolated from wilting *Medicago sativa* plants

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Abstract

The study focused on the isolation, characterization and conservation of fungal strains isolated from *Medicago sativa* plants showing wilt disease symptoms in southern Tunisian oases. A total of 79 fungal strains were isolated from different plant organs, including roots, collars, and stems. Morphological identification of fungal strains was based on the morphology of culture on PDA medium and of the conidia under microscope. All the fungal strains were stored on PDA slant covered with mineral oil at room temperature. Over all, three main fungal genera were identified i.e. *Fusarium* sp., *Rhizoctonia* sp., and *Alternaria* sp. with unidentified strains. These findings demonstrate that alfalfa wilt disease is probably caused by a complex of pathogens rather than the effect of a single pathogen.

Keywords: Alfalfa, Endophytic fungi, Morphological identification, Wilt disease.

1. Introduction

Medicago is an important forage legume that is widely distributed across Tunisia, in all bioclimatic zones (**Seklani and Hassan, 1990**). The perennial species *Medicago sativa* is most widely cultivated forage legume in the oases in the south of the country. Alfalfa crops enhance soil structure, boost fertility, and minimize erosion, making them an important component of crop rotations and sustainable agricultural systems (**Samac and al.2002**). However, many diseases caused by fungi, in particular root rot and wilt symptoms, affect *Medicago sativa* growth and seed production. Thus, the precise identification of the causal agents constitutes the first step in establishing a control strategy. Morphological identification remains the most commonly used and cheap method that can be easily established for the identification of fungi (**Fischer and Dott, 2002**).

So, the objectives of this study was to identify fungal strains, based on morphology of culture and conidia, associated with wilt disease of alfalfa in southern Tunisian oases and to establish a core collection of fungal strains to be used in future research programs for the control of wilt disease of alfalfa. .

2. Material and methods

2.1. Origin of plant samples

Medicago sativa plants showing symptoms of wilting were collected from six oases located in southern Tunisia in the following regions: Tozeur (2 sites) and Kebeli (4 sites). The samples were separated and identified according to their location (Table 1).

2.2. Isolation of fungal strains

Plant organs (root, collar, and basal stems) were surface-sterilized in 70 % ethanol (v/v) for 30 s followed by submerging in 3 % sodium hypochlorite solution (NaOCl) for 5 min then rinsed at least 5 times with sterile distilled water. Each plant organ was cut into small pieces, placed on PDA medium supplemented with antibiotics (0.5 % Streptomycin) and incubated at 25 °C for 5-7 days. The growing fungal colonies were purified by serial sub-culturing on the same medium.

2.3. Conservation of fungal cultures

Long-term conservation of the isolated fungal strains was carried out under a layer of sterile mineral oil (Cavalcanti, 1991; Silva et al., 1994). Tubes with PDA slant were inoculated with 7 to 10 days old fungal culture and then incubated at 25 °C for 14 days. Then after, the fungal culture was covered with sterile mineral oil, which was autoclaved twice (20 min at 120 °C) and dehumidified for 8 hours at 120 °C. Tubes were stored in an upright position at room temperature.

2.4. Macroscopic and microscopic examination of fungal strains

The morphology of fungal cultures was characterized macroscopically by describing the colony color, shape and size. The microscopic examination was carried out by observing the conidiophores, conidia and mycelia morphologies and sizes under the "Hund wetzlar" microscope at 400x magnification in a methylene blue solution.

3. Results

A total of 79 fungal strains associated with wilt disease symptoms (foliage yellowing and roots rot) were isolated from diseased alfalfa plants in southern Tunisia oases. The morphology of fungal cultures and microscopic structure are presented in Table 2. Morphological identification of fungi isolated from the diseased alfalfa plants revealed that the majority of them belong to three genera, of *Fusarium* sp., *Rhizoctonia* sp. and *Alternaria* sp.

The morphology of *Fusarium* cultures are consistent with that described in the literature (**Leslie and Summerell, 2006; Nelson et al. 1983**). The color of *Fusarium* cultures on PDA varied from white to reddish and purple colors. The microconidia, were mainly unicellular with oval, fusoid, pyriform to obovate shapes. The macroconidia was rarely observed. A wide and straight shape with blunt and rounded apical cell and barely notched or rounded basal cell was noticed in some isolates (Figure 2). A curved shape with curved and pointed apical cell was perceived in some others. Chlamydospores are more common in older cultures than younger ones on PDA. It is easy to confuse true chlamydospores, pseudochlamydospores, and swollen cells as they often appear similar. Chlamydospores are globose in shape, single, paired or in chains, smooth walled sometimes clustered.

The *Alternaria* culture is characterized by a black to olivaceous-black or greyish surface on top and a black color at the back of the plate. Conidia are obclavate, obpyriform, sometimes ovoid or ellipsoidal, and have a long conical or cylindrical beak. Simple, branched, short or elongate conidiophores generate sympodially branched acropetal chains (blastocatenate) of multicellular conidia (dictyoconidia) (**Naho and al. 2009**) (Figure 1).

The *Rhizoctonia* cultures had different colony color and sclerotia color, density and size. The color of a young colony is white, whereas the color of an older isolation is brown. The hues of the colonies are white to cream. All *Rhizoctonia* strains did not produce conidia, the hyphae is formed by long tube with septa inside. The hyphae branches had taper shape, a constriction at the basis and perpendicular angles (**Djebali et al., 2014**) (Figure 1).

4. Discussion

Wilting disease in alfalfa cultivation became a serious problem in the Southern oases of Tunisia. Indeed, the field surveys showed that the six prospected oases in 2019 had alfalfa plants with typical symptoms of wilting and root rot (unpublished data), however the incidence of the

disease had not been evaluated. The isolation of fungi showed different morphologies in cultures and conidia demonstrating that alfalfa wilt disease is a complex disease rather than the effect of a single pathogen. Overall, 79 fungal strains were isolated from roots, collars, and stems of diseased alfalfa plants.

A morphological analysis based on colony and fungal structures morphologies using determination keys was used to identify the fungal species at the genus level. The majority of fungal strains belong to three main genera *Fusarium* sp., *Rhizoctonia* sp. and *Alternaria* sp. The PDA medium was used to observe and cultivate all fungi because of its suitability for the culture of a wide range of fungal species (Dhingra and Sinclair, 1985; Ganjar et al., 1999), but for accurate identification of fungal strains especially of the *Fusarium* genus we should use other selective media like Carnation leaf Agar (CLA) (Leslie and Summerell, 2006).

The morphological fungal identification is effective for rapid and costless characterization of pathogens at the genus level (Wang et al., 2016). However, it is not so obvious when the identification of the fungi strains is needed at the species level (Lutzoni et al., 2004). So, the molecular identification of all fungal strains used in this study will be done through the sequencing of ITS genes.

5. Conclusion

The isolation and identification of filamentous fungus from wilting alfalfa plants collected from the southern Tunisian oases revealed a plethora of fungi with a large biodiversity, demonstrating that alfalfa wilt disease is probably caused by a complex of fungal pathogens. In order to confirm that the pathogenicity of the isolated strains along with their molecular identification will be done in future research work. In addition, the fungal collection setup is a mandatory tool that supports all future works to reach the final goal of finding appropriate control methods of wilt disease in alfalfa in order to promote the cultivation of this valuable forage legume in Southern regions of Tunisia. .

6. References

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Figure 1: *Rhizoctonia sp* and *Alternaria sp* fungal strains, (a,b,e,h,i) : Colonies grown on PDA medium of (a) TZ 1 MS T3.②; (b) TZ 1 MS T4; (e) KB 2 MS R1; (h, i) DZ 1.1 MS T3.②.② : Top and reverse view ; (c, d) Hyphae: Long tube with septa or partition inside; Young hyphae forming 45° angle (Arrow) ; (f, g) Conidia of DZ 1.2 MS C2.①.② strain; (j) Conidia of DZ 1.1 MS T3.②.② strain

Figure 2: *Fusarium sp* fungal strains, (a, e, h, k, o) Top view of colonies grown on PDA medium of (a) TZ 1 MS T1; (e) DZ 1.2 MS R2(2); (h) TZ 2 MS T1.(2).(2); (k) TZ 1 MS C1.(2); (o) DZ 1.2 MS R4.(1).(2); (b, f, l, p) Reverse view of (b) TZ 1 MS T1; (f) DZ 1.2 MS R2(2); (i) TZ 2 MS T1.(2).(2); (p) DZ 1.2 MS R4.(1).(2); (c, d, g, j, m, n, q) Micro and macroconidia of (c, d) TZ 1 MS T1; (g) DZ 1.2 MS R2(2); (j) TZ 2 MS T1.(2).(2); (m, n) DZ 1.2 MS R2(1); (q) DZ 1.2 MS R4.(1).(2); (l) Paired chlamydospores of TZ 1 MS C1.(2) strain

Table 1: Geographic locations of wilted *M.sativa* plants samples

Samples ID	Oases locations	Plant organs	GPS Coordinates	
			Longitude	Latitude
DZ1.1	Douz 1	Collar, stem and roots	9.021792	33.447903
DZ1.2	Douz 2	Collar, stem and roots	9.022600	33.448253
KB 2	Kebili	Collar, stem and roots	8.959338	33.696817
SA 1	Souk Ahad	Stem	8.865141	33.766433
TZ 1	Tozeur 1	Collar, stem and roots	8.163181	33.935854
TZ 2	Tozeur 2	Collar, stem and roots	8.114975	33.895391

Table 2: The macroscopic and microscopic characterization of fungal strains isolated from *Medicago sativa* wilting plants collected from southern Tunisia oases.

no.	Strain ID	Location	Plant Organ	Fungal colony morphology (color/Aspect)	Fungal structure	Description	Genus
1	DZ 1.1 MS C1.①	Kebili / Douz	Collar	White Produces brown pigment in the media	Macroconidia	Shape : Wide and straight Apical cell : Blunt and rounded Foot : Barely notched or rounded end Size : $47.5\pm 2.5 \times 5.9\pm 0.5$	<i>Fusarium</i>
					Microconidia	Shape : Oval Phialide : Monophialide	
					Chlamydo spores	Globose in shape Paired, smooth walled	
2	DZ 1.1 MS C1.②	Kebili/ Douz	Collar	White	Macroconidia	Shape : Wide and straight Apical : Blunt and rounded Foot: Barely notched or rounded end 5-6 septate Size : $54.5\pm 2.5 \times 5.9\pm 0.5$	<i>Fusarium</i>
					Microconidia	Shape : Two to three celled-oval Phialide : Monophialides	
					Chlamydo spores	Globose in shape Clustred	
3	DZ 1.1 MS C2	Kebili/ Douz	Collar	Thick white tufts Reverse view : Central half appearing brownish Strong odor	Microconidia	Shape : Ovoid to ellipsoid predominantly 0-septate to rarely 3-septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
4	DZ 1.1 MS C3.①	Kebili/ Douz	Collar	White Irregular pattern Reverse view : Central half appearing brownish Strong odor	Microconidia	Shape : Ovoid to ellipsoid predominantly 0-septate to rarely 3-septate Phialide : Monophialides	<i>Fusarium</i>

no.	Strain ID	Location	Plant Organ	Fungal colony morphology (color/Aspect)	Fungal structure	Description	Genus
5	DZ 1.1 MS C4.①	Kebili/ Douz	Collar	White, Convex Aerial mycelia dense Reverse view: Pale orange in the center, white at the margin.			Unknown
6	DZ 1.1 MS R1.①	Kebili/ Douz	Root	Yellowish white Reverse view: Light orange and yellowish spots	Microconidia	Oval, reniform, elongated oval to sometimes obovoid with a truncate base, mostly 0-septate Size : 22.6±7×6.8±1.4	<i>Fusarium</i>
7	DZ 1.1 MS R1.②	Kebili/ Douz	Root	Yellowish white	Macroconidia	Falcate, dorsiventral, with 3–5 septate and mostly 5-septate Apical cell : pointed, tapered, and curved Foot cell: Well-developed. Relatively wide Size : 50.2±2.5×5.8±0.5	<i>Fusarium</i>
					Microconidia	Oval, reniform, elongated oval to sometimes obovoid with a truncate base, mostly 0-septate	
8	DZ 1.1 MS R2.①.①	Kebili/ Douz	Root	White , slightly pink in the center	Microconidia	Ovoid to ellipsoid predominantly 0-septate Abundant microconidia Size : 6.4±1.9×3.1±0.7	<i>Fusarium</i>

no.	Strain ID	Location	Plant Organ	Fungal colony morphology (color/Aspect)	Fungal structure	Description	Genus
9	DZ 1.1 MS R2.①.②	Kebili/ Douz	Root	White or slightly pink aerial mycelium Lanose aspect Reverse view: Salmon colored	Microconidia	Shape: Obovoid , mostly non-septate or occasionally with one septum	<i>Fusarium</i>
10	DZ 1.1 MS R2.②.①	Kebili/ Douz	Root	Thick white tuft with violet color in the center	Microconidia	Shape : Ovoid to ellipsoid predominantly 0-septate to rarely 3-septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
11	DZ 1.1 MS R2.②.②	Kebili/ Douz	Root	White Sparse mycelia in the center	Microconidia	Ovoid to ellipsoid predominantly 0-septate to rarely 3-septate Phialide : Monophialides	<i>Fusarium</i>
12	DZ 1.1 MS R3.①	Kebili/ Douz	Root	White Becomes yellowish-orange white with time	Microconidia	Shape :Two to three celled-oval Phialide : Monophialides, often quite long	<i>Fusarium</i>
					Chlamydo spores	Globose in shape Paired, smooth walled	
13	DZ 1.1 MS R3.②	Kebili/ Douz	Root	Yellowish white Convex, aerial mycelia dense Reverse view: Light orange in the center, yellowish white at the margin.	Microconidia	Shape: Ovoid to ellipsoid Size: 14.3±1.5×6.1±1.5	<i>Fusarium</i>
14	DZ 1.1 MS R4.①	Kebili/ Douz	Root	White	Chlamydo spores	Globose in shape Paired, smooth walled	<i>Fusarium</i>

no.	Strain ID	Location	Plant Organ	Fungal colony morphology (color/Aspect)	Fungal structure	Description	Genus
15	DZ 1.2 MS R4.①.②	Kebili/ Douz	Root	White to pinkish white	Macroconidia	Falcate and thin walled Apical cell : bent Basal cell : Foot shaped	
					Microconidia	Shape : Oval, allantoid and fusoid 0 septate	
16	DZ 1.1 MS R4.②	Kebili/ Douz	Root	Aerial mycelium pinkish-white, loosely lanose	Microconidia	Shape : Oval, allantoid and fusoid 0 septate Size: 6.6±2×4.1±1.1	<i>Fusarium</i>
17	DZ 1.1 MS T2.①	Kebili/ Douz	Stem	Olivaceous brown to black Sparse aerial mycelium.	Conidiophores	simple conidiophores	<i>Alternaria</i>
18	DZ 1.1 MS T2.②	Kebili/ Douz	Stem	White , convex, aerial mycelia dense, colony margin lobate	Macroconidia	Dorsiventral curvature, smooth, hyaline Apical cell: hooked to tapering Basal cell : Foot-shaped 3–5-septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
19	DZ 1.1 MS T3	Kebili/ Douz	Stem	White to pale violet with dark magenta color in the center	Microconidia	Shape : Ovoid to ellipsoid predominantly 0-septate to rarely 3-septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
20	DZ 1.1 MS T3.①.①	Kebili/ Douz	Stem	Olivaceous brown to black Sparse aerial mycelium.	Conidia	Produced on surface in short chains of 2–5 maximum 8, on short, simple conidiophores Conidia are brown to dark brown, ovoid, obclavate to subcylindrical	<i>Alternaria</i>

no.	Strain ID	Location	Plant Organ	Fungal colony morphology (color/Aspect)	Fungal structure	Description	Genus
21	DZ 1.1 MS T3.②.②	Kebili/ Douz	Stem	Olivaceous grey Sparse aerial mycelium.	Conidia	Brown to dark brown, ovoid, obclavate to subcylindrical conidia Produced on surface in short chains of 2–5 maximum 8, on short conidiophores With transverse and longitudinal septa.	<i>Alternaria</i>
22	DZ 1.1 MS T4	Kebili/ Douz	Stem	Thick white tufts	Microconidia	Shape : Ovoid to ellipsoid predominantly 0-septate to rarely 3-septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
23	DZ 1.1 MS T5.①	Kebili/ Douz	Stem	Thick white tufts with pale violet color in the center	Microconidia	Shape : Ovoid to ellipsoid predominantly 0-septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
24	DZ 1.1 MS T5.②	Kebili/ Douz	Stem	White	Chlamydo spores	Usually present at the end of hyphae Singly and smooth walled	<i>Fusarium</i>
25	DZ 1.1 MS T7.1	Kebili/ Douz	Stem	Thick white tufts	Chlamydo spores	Usually present at the end of hyphae Single or paired and smooth walled	<i>Fusarium</i>
26	DZ 1.2 MS C1.①	Kebili/ Douz	Collar	White ,convex, aerial mycelia dense Reverse: pale orange in the center, white at the margin.	Microconidia	Oval, elongated oval to sometimes clavate with a truncate base mostly 0–1 septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
27	DZ 1.2 MS C1.②	Kebili/ Douz	Collar	White Aerial mycelia dense Reverse view: Light orange and yellowish spots	Microconidia	Clavate with truncate bases mostly 0–1 septate Abundant microconidia	<i>Fusarium</i>

no.	Strain ID	Location	Plant Organ	Fungal colony morphology (color/Aspect)	Fungal structure	Description	Genus
28	DZ 1.2 MS C2	Kebili/ Douz	Collar	Yellowish white Convex, aerial mycelia dense Reverse view: Light orange in the center, yellowish white at the margin.	Microconidia	Ovoid to ellipsoid predominantly 0-1 septate to rarely 3-septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
29	DZ 1.2 MS C2.①.①	Kebili/ Douz	Collar	White ,convex, aerial mycelia dense Reverse: pale orange in the center, white at the margin.	Chlamydo spores	Globose in shape Single, paired or in short chains	<i>Fusarium</i>
30	DZ 1.2 MS C2.①.②	Kebili/ Douz	Collar	Light grey, with Olivaceous brown to black spots	Conidia	Dark brown, obpyriform, smooth surface, long beak With transverse and longitudinal septa.	<i>Alternaria</i>
31	DZ 1.2 MS C3	Kebili/ Douz	Collar	White The hyphae initially were hyaline. Mycelium becomes yellowish white and yellowish in reverse with time.	Micoconidia Chlamydo spores	Oval, elongated oval to sometimes clavate with a truncate base mostly 0–1 septate Globose in shape Single	<i>Fusarium</i>
32	DZ 1.2 MS R1	Kebili/ Douz	Root	White Reverse: Yellowish-orange in the center, white at the margin.	Micoconidia	Oval, Ovoid to ellipsoid mostly 0–2 septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
33	DZ 1.2 MS R1.①.①	Kebili/ Douz	Root	White	Micoconidia	Shape : Oval, allantoid and fusoid 0 septate Abundant microconidia	<i>Fusarium</i>

no.	Strain ID	Location	Plant Organ	Fungal colony morphology (color/Aspect)	Fungal structure	Description	Genus
34	DZ 1.2 MS R1.①.②	Kebili/ Douz	Root	Black, sparse aerial mycelium.	Conidia	Brown to dark brown, ovoid, obclavate to subcylindrical conidia Produced on surface in short chains of 2–5 maximum 8, on short conidiophores With transverse and longitudinal septa. Presence of subcylindrical, mature conidium	<i>Alternaria</i>
35	DZ 1.2 MS R2①	Kebili/ Douz	Root	white with with pale violet color in the center Pinkish white in the reverse view	Macroconidia	Apical cell : Curved Basal cell : Barely notched and pointed Mostly 3-5 septate Size : $42.5 \pm 2.5 \times 5.1 \pm 0.5$	<i>Fusarium</i>
					Microconidia	Elongated oval and obovoid with a truncate base	
36	DZ 1.2 MS R2②	Kebili/ Douz	Root	White to pinkish white	Macroconidia	Falcate and thin walled Apical cell : bent Basal cell : Foot shaped	<i>Fusarium</i>
					Microconidia	Shape : Oval, allantoid and fusoid 0 septate	
37	DZ 1.2 MS R3	Kebili/ Douz	Root	Olivaceous brown Reverse view: Dark brown to black	Conidia	Short chains of obclavate to subcylindrical conidia	<i>Alternaria</i>

no.	Strain ID	Location	Plant Organ	Fungal colony morphology (color/Aspect)	Fungal structure	Description	Genus
38	DZ 1.2 MS R4.①.①	Kebili/ Douz	Root	Olivaceous brown to black Sparse aerial mycelium.	Conidia	Brown to dark brown, ovoid, obclavate to subcylindrical conidia Produced on surface in short chains of 2–5 maximum 8, on short conidiophores With transverse and longitudinal septa. Presence of subcylindrical, mature conidium	<i>Alternaria</i>
39	DZ 1.2 MS R2	Kebili/ Douz	Root	White Pinkish white in the reverse view Light orange pigment in the agar	Micoconidia	Shape : Oval, allantoid and fusoid 0 septate Abundant microconidia Size : 7.5±1.7×3.9±0.4	<i>Fusarium</i>
40	DZ 1.2 MS R5	Kebili/ Douz	Root	White Reverse : Pink	Microconidia	Shape : Oval, allantoid and fusoid 0 septate Abandunt microconidia Size: 7±1.1×3.2±0.4	<i>Fusarium</i>
41	DZ 1.2 MS T1.②	Kebili/ Douz	Stem	White Reverse view : Yellowish-orange in the center with sometimes brown spots	Microconidia	Shape : Ovoid to ellipsoid 3-5 septate Abandunt microconidia	<i>Fusarium</i>

no.	Strain ID	Location	Plant Organ	Fungal colony morphology (color/Aspect)	Fungal structure	Description	Genus
42	DZ 1.2 MS T2.①.①	Kebili/ Douz	Stem	White, floccose, radiate, with abundant aerial mycelium, margin irregular, lobate, serrate or filiform. Reverse view: Pale yellow to yellow with yellow diffusible pigments visible in the medium.	Macroconidia	Hyaline, falcate, curved dorsiventrally, tapering towards both ends Apical cell : blunt and straight to slightly curved Basal cell : blunt to barely notched, smooth- and thin-walled 3–5-septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
43	DZ 1.2 MS T2.①.②	Kebili/ Douz	Stem	Pinkish white, Aerial mycelia dense slightly raised, colony margin undulate, radially striated Reverse view: greyish yellow in the center, pinkish white at the margin.	Macroconidia	Falcate, slightly curved to dorsiventral curvature, slightly rough, hyaline Apical cell : hooked to tapering Basal cell : foot-shaped 5-septate: 39.5 ±6.1×4±1.4	<i>Fusarium</i>
					Chlamydo spores	Abundant, intercalarily or terminal, ellipsoid, globose, smooth, thick-walled, hyaline 0–2-septate	
44	DZ 1.2 MS T2.②	Kebili/ Douz	Stem	White , slightly raised , Reverse view: greyish yellow in the center, Slight yellow to pale- brown pigmentation in the agar	Chlamydo spores	Abundant, intercalarily or terminal, ellipsoid, globose, smooth, thick-walled, hyaline 0–2-septate	<i>Fusarium</i>

no.	Strain ID	Location	Plant Organ	Fungal colony morphology (color/Aspect)	Fungal structure	Description	Genus
45	DZ 1.2 MS T3.①	Kebili/ Douz	Stem	Yellowish white Reverse view: Brownish yellow in the center, yellowish white at the margin.	Chlamydo spores	Globose, smooth, thick-walled Single	<i>Fusarium</i>
47	TZ 2 MS C2	Tozeur/Tozeur	Collar	white	Microconidia	Shape : Ovoid to ellipsoid predominantly 0-septate to rarely 3-septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
48	TZ 2 MS R1.①	Tozeur/Tozeur	Root	white	Microconidia	Oval, reniform, elongated oval to sometimes obovoid with a truncate base, mostly 0-septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
49	TZ 2 MS R1.②	Tozeur/Tozeur	Root	White	Macroconidia	Shape : Wide and straight Apical cell : Blunt and rounded Foot : Barely notched or rounded end Attached chlamydo spores	<i>Fusarium</i>
					Microconidia	Oval, reniform, elongated oval to sometimes obovoid with a truncate base, mostly 0-septate occasionally with 1 or septa	
					Chlamydo spores	Globose, subglobose, intercalary or terminal and rough walled, within the macroconidia	
50	TZ 2 MS R2.①.①	Tozeur/Tozeur	Root	White Sparse mycelia	Microconidia	Shape : Oval, allantoid and fusoid 0 septate	<i>Fusarium</i>

no.	Strain ID	Location	Plant Organ	Fungal colony morphology (color/Aspect)	Fungal structure	Description	Genus
51	TZ 2 MS R2.②	Tozeur/Tozeur	Root	White The hyphae initially were hyaline. Mycelium becomes yellowish white and yellowish in reverse.	Microconidia	Oval, elongated oval to sometimes clavate with a truncate base mostly 0–1-septate Size: 39.5±8.2×15±2.5	<i>Fusarium</i>
52	TZ 2 MS T1.②.②	Tozeur/Tozeur	Stem	Saffron to pale orange, white at the margin Flat, felty to velvety, radiate, with aerial mycelium	Macroconidia	Falcate, slender, curved dorsoventrally, tapering towards both ends, Apical cell : elongate or whip-like curved Basal cell : Barely notched to prominently extended 3–6 septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
					Chlamydo spores	Globose, subglobose to oval, subhyaline, smooth-walled, terminal or intercalary, solitary or in pairs forming chains	
53	TZ 2 MS T2.②	Tozeur/Tozeur	Stem	White , flat, felty to velvety, radiate			Unknown
54	KB 2 MS C1	Kebili/ Kebili	Collar	White Slight yellow to pale- brown pigmentation in the agar	Chlamydo spores	Abundant, intercalarily or terminal, ellipsoid, globose, smooth, thick-walled, hyaline 0–2-septate	<i>Fusarium</i>

no.	Strain ID	Location	Plant Organ	Fungal colony morphology (color/Aspect)	Fungal structure	Description	Genus
55	KB 2 MS C2	Kebili/ Kebili	Collar	Cream color Sclerotial color : Pale brown Distribution of sclerotia : circular concentrated sparse	Mycelia and sclerotia	Hyphae: long tube with septa or partition inside. The branches of hyphae were tapered and perpendicular angles.	<i>Rhizoctonia</i>
56	KB 2 MS R	Kebili/ Kebili	Root	Olivaceous brown to black Sparse aerial mycelium.	Conidia	Brown to dark brown, ovoid, obclavate to subcylindrical conidia Produced on surface in short chains of 2–5 maximum 8, on short conidiophores With transverse and longitudinal septa.	<i>Alternaria</i>
57	KB 2 MS R1	Kebili/ Kebili	Root	Greyish black in the center and white at the margin.			<i>Alternaria</i>
58	KB 2 MS R3	Kebili/ Kebili	Root	Greyish black in the center and white at the margin.			<i>Alternaria</i>
59	KB 2 MS R.a	Kebili/ Kebili	Root	White	Macroconidia	Falcate , the central two cells are almost straight and are widest in the middle Apical cell :curved Basal cell : Rounded to barely foot shaped Number of septa : 3-5 septa Size : 7.2±0.76×3±0.47	<i>Fusarium</i>

no.	Strain ID	Location	Plant Organ	Fungal colony morphology (color/Aspect)	Fungal structure	Description	Genus
60	KB 2 MS R.b	Kebili/ Kebili	Root	White	Macroconidia	Falcate , the central two cells are almost straight and are widest in the middle Apical cell :curved Basal cell : Rounded to barely foot shaped Number of septa : 3-5 septa Size : 9.1±1.8×3.4±0.68	<i>Fusarium</i>
61	KB 2 MS T	Kebili/ Kebili	Stem	White Brown pigment produced in the agar Abundant dense aerial mycelia	Macroconidia	Falcate, slender, straight to curved, smooth to slightly rough Apical cell : blunt or hooked Basal cell : barely notched 3-5-septate; 3-septate macroconidia : 27.5±1.2×4.5±0.5	<i>Fusarium</i>
62	KB 2 MS T 1	Kebili/ Kebili	Stem	White , Brownish yellow in the center, floccose	Microconidia	Shape : Ovoid , elongated ovoid to ellipsoid 3-5 septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
63	SA 1 MS T1.1	Kebili/ Souk Ahad	Stem	White Convex, aerial mycelia dense, colony margin lobate Reverse view : Yellow			Unknown
64	SA 1 MS T1.2	Kebili/ Souk Ahad	Stem	White Abundant mycelium	Microconidia	Ellipsoidal to club shaped 0-4 septate	<i>Fusarium</i>

no.	Strain ID	Location	Plant Organ	Fungal colony morphology (color/Aspect)	Fungal structure	Description	Genus
65	SA 1 MS T2.1	Kebili/ Souk Ahad	Stem	Olivaceous brown to black Sparse aerial mycelium.	Conidiophores	Simple conidiophores	<i>Alternaria</i>
66	SA 1 MS T3.1	Kebili/ Souk Ahad	Stem	Cream color Sclerotial color : white and pale brown Distribution of sclerotia : rare concentric rings	Mycelia and sclerotia	Hyphae: long tube with septa or partition inside. The branches of hyphae were tapered and perpendicular angles.	<i>Rhizoctonia</i>
67	SA 1 MS T3.2	Kebili/ Souk Ahad	Stem	White , flat, felty to velvety, radiate, with aerial mycelium	Chlamydospores	Globose, subglobose to oval, subhyaline, smooth-walled, terminal or intercalary, solitary or in pairs forming chains	<i>Fusarium</i>
68	TZ 1 MS C1.①	Tozeur/Tozeur	Collar	White, becomes pale brown with age Forms a pale brown to dark brown pigment	Chlamydospores	In chains or in clumps Abundant mycelium	<i>Fusarium</i>
69	TZ 1 MS C1.②	Tozeur/Tozeur	Collar	White, becomes pale brown with age Pale brown to dark brown pigment Dark spots or flecks of pigment are formed in the agar	Chlamydospores	Paired or in chains Abundant mycelium	<i>Fusarium</i>

no.	Strain ID	Location	Plant Organ	Fungal colony morphology (color/Aspect)	Fungal structure	Description	Genus
70	TZ 1 MS C2.①	Tozeur/Tozeur	Collar	White to slight yellow Pale brown to dark brown spots in the reverse view	Chlamydo spores	Abundant, intercalarily or terminal, ellipsoid, globose, smooth, thick-walled, hyaline, 0–2-septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
71	TZ 1 MS C2.②	Tozeur/Tozeur	Collar	White , abundant aerial mycelium	Chlamydo spores	Globose, subglobose to oval, subhyaline, smooth-walled, terminal or intercalary, solitary or in pairs forming chains	<i>Fusarium</i>
72	TZ 1 MS R	Tozeur/Tozeur	Root	White with violet /pink color in the center abundant aerial mycelium	Microconidia	Shape : Ovoid to ellipsoid predominantly 0-septate to rarely 3-septate Size : 7.7±1.6×3.3±0.6	<i>Fusarium</i>
73	TZ 1 MS T1	Tozeur/Tozeur	Stem	White to slight yellow , spots of pale-brown pigmentation	Macroconidia	Curved Unequal dorsiventral curvature ; Upper wall is curved and the lower wall is almost straight Curved and pointed Notched , occasionally foot shaped 5 septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
					Microconidia	Phialide :Polyphialides, tree-like appearance	
					Chlamydo spores	Chains of verrucose chlamydo spores	
74	TZ 1 MS T2.①	Tozeur/Tozeur	Stem	White with rose to burgundy pigment	Microconidia	Shape : Straight, no septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
75	TZ 1 MS T2.②	Tozeur/Tozeur	Stem	White , flat, felty to velvety colony margin undulate			Unknown

no.	Strain ID	Location	Plant Organ	Fungal colony morphology (color/Aspect)	Fungal structure	Description	Genus
76	TZ 1 MS T3.②	Tozeur/Tozeur	Stem	Cream color Sclerotial color : Dark brown Distribution of sclerotia : circular concentrated circle	Mycelia and sclerotia	Hyphae: Long tube with septa or partition inside. The young hyphae had branches forming 45° angles, the more mature branches were perpendicular and same size.	<i>Rhizoctonia</i>
77	TZ 1 MS T3.a	Tozeur/Tozeur	Stem	White Reverse view : Spots appearing brownish reddish or orange	Microconidia	Shape : Ovoid to ellipsoid predominantly 0-septate to rarely 3-septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
78	TZ 1 MS T3.b	Tozeur/Tozeur	Stem	White Colony reverse : spots appearing brownish reddish or orange	Microconidia	Shape : Ovoid to ellipsoid predominantly 0-septate to rarely 3-septate	<i>Fusarium</i>
79	TZ 1 MS T4	Tozeur/Tozeur	Stem	White Sclerotial color : White Distribution of sclerotia : wide sparsely	Mycelia and sclerotia	Hyphae: Long tube and septa or partition inside. The branches of hyphae were tapered and perpendicular angles	<i>Rhizoctonia</i>
80	DZ 1.2 MS R4.②	Kebili/ Douz	Root	White to pinkish white	Microconidia	Shape : Oval, allantoid and fusoid 0 septate Abandunt microconidia Size: 7.9±1×5.3±0.35	<i>Fusarium</i>

Size : Length×width (µm)

